

Original Article

GREEN GOVERNANCE AND SUSTAINABILITY OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

Ezinne Mary Kekeocha, Ezimma K. Nnabuife, Daniel Chukwuma Ejike

Department of Business Administration

Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Email: me.kekeocha@unizik.edu.ng/

ezimmnabuife@gmail.com/

dc.ejike@unizike.edu.ng

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024247>

Abstract: This study examined the relationship that exists between Green Governance and Sustainability of SMEs in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives include; determining the relationship between green human resources management (GHRM) Practice on employee retention as well as the relationship that exists between environmental stewardship on eco-innovation in SMEs in Anambra State, Nigeria. The Study was anchored on stakeholder's theory, by Freeman in (1984) and employed descriptive survey research design and systematic sampling technique. The population of the study was 243 while the sample size was 151 employees from Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 27). Findings indicate that Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practice has significant and positive effect on employee retention of Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State, and environmental stewardship also has significant and positive effect on eco-innovation of Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State. The study therefore, concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between green governance and sustainability of SMEs in the Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study recommended that Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State should adopt green governance policies to address the needs of the employees toward achieving sustainability in their performance. It is also necessary to recognize the importance of environmental stewardship toward achieving core capacities and values through eco-innovation that could result to the sustainability of the business operation.

Keywords: Green Governance, Sustainability, SMEs, Green Human Resources management practice (GHRM), Employee Retention, Environmental Stewardship and Eco-innovation.

Original Article

Introduction

The field of green governance is rapidly gaining traction among academics and is progressively becoming a central focus for policymaking in both private and public institutions worldwide. Companies and corporate organizations are increasingly acknowledging that their relentless pursuit of production and profit has caused them more harm than good, contributing to issues like global warming and environmental degradation. Therefore, the need to promote green practices that can preserve natural resources, while production and consumption is taking place is vital to the sustainability of any business (Amandeep and Mishra, 2019). Green governance is a concept that bridges conflicts between human and nature through a set of institution's rules (Chairina and Tjahjadi, 2023). Furthermore, it ensures that decision-making maintain sustainable operations in terms of the economic, social and environmental aspects of the business. Green governance serves as a pivotal instrument in attaining sustainable development and outlines an efficient pathway towards achieving it (Xu and Zhu, 2022). Achieving efficiency in green governance is crucial for achieving sustainable growth, as it merges environmental sustainability with economic development. On the other hand, insufficient or lack of green governance policies may result in environmental, social, and economic setbacks, posing a threat to sustainable development (Sueyoshi, Goto, and Wang, 2017).

Sustainability is defined as addressing the requirements of a company's direct and indirect stakeholders (including employees, clients, pressure groups, communities, etc.), while ensuring that the company's capacity to meet the needs of future stakeholders remains intact (Martins, Branco, Melo and Machado, 2022). Organizational sustainability implies having in place the right leadership style, talents, global awareness/intuition and the action plan required in combating threats being faced by modern organizations (Genty, 2021). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) vary widely in terms of their size and structure and they represent a diverse range of companies, each presenting unique challenges and opportunities in the implementation of sustainability-oriented actions (Koirala, 2019). The definition of SMEs also varies from country to country, reflecting the economic, cultural, and social characteristics of each nation, and is typically based on factors such as the value of assets or the number of employees (Chege and Wang, 2022). SMEs have the capacity to tackle sustainable development issues within communities, drive transformations towards sustainability and exhibit distinct characteristics that set them apart from larger corporations (Westman, et. al. (2019).

Furthermore, engaging the entire spectrum of SMEs in developing sustainable solutions to thrive in a dynamic and competitive environment poses a significant challenge (Chege and Wang, 2022). These challenges include; lack of institutional support, the absence of perceived business benefits from sustainability practices, and the lack of frameworks and guidelines tailored to assist SMEs in planning, monitoring, and evaluating their sustainability efforts. Perhaps, achieving sustainable development in SMEs, requires the adoption of polices and decisions that aims at addressing Green human resource Management (GHRM) practices to achieve employee retention and environmental stewardship through adoption of eco-innovation in SMEs, especially, plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Green HRM refers to the systematic, deliberate integration of traditional human resources management techniques with the company's environmental objectives (Khan, Zubair and Khan, 2021). The objective of GHRM is to motivate the workers and create a sense of pride in them as part of sustainable development. Furthermore, GHRM helps to create brand images of a company, upgrade

Original Article

the morale of the workers, retain talent and finally help to attract competitive employees (Kumar et.al, 2023). Imevbore, (2020) define environmental stewardship as the responsible use and protection of natural environment through conservation and sustainable practice. Environmental stewardship entails taking action to accommodate and balance the requirements of various groups, while also ensuring the consistent conservation and responsible use of natural resources (Olubodun and Agbaje, 2021). Furthermore, it is also the responsible management of human activities affecting the environment, aimed at conserving and preserving natural resources for the benefit of present and future generations, while being accountable to society. It also encourages firms to proactively design their operations, taking the initiative rather than waiting to be compelled by government regulations or customer demands for stewardship activities (Olubodun and Agbaje, 2021).

Human resources are important assets of an organization. Therefore, higher turnover rates of skilled workers in an organization create vacuum that will take time to fill at an additional cost (Jobalise, Chukwuka and Emmanuel, 2018). Nwangsari and Sutuwajiya, (2019) posit that employee retention is the process of implementing the GHRM practices by organizations in order to reduce turnover rate of employees and stop them from leaving the organization. Management has a direct impact on the organization's ability to retain or lose its workforce and the way human resources are managed in an organization creates the terms and conditions of the employee-employer relationship (Adeyefa, 2023).

Eco-innovation was first introduced by James Fussler in 1996 and it helps in reducing environmental risk, pollution and other negative impacts of energy use without undermining economic performance (Nosheen and Abid, 2023). Eco-innovation is important for sustainable environmental protection, through which improvements in production processes and product portfolio are achieved. Firms need to incorporate eco-innovation into their business by themselves or through collaboration to provide competitive edge to businesses, improve resource efficiency and environmental performance of the firms (Calza et. al, (2017).

Statement of the Problem

Environmental concerns and the imperative for sustainable business practices are gaining momentum globally among manufacturing firms, both small and large ones. Unfortunately, firms in Anambra State, especially those in SMEs sector appears not to be interested in adopting green governance policy, which from all indications assures business sustainability. According to Saliem, (2020), firms that adopt green human resource policies often gain through their employees who are always conscious of the environment.

The increasing environmental degradation and health hazards resulting from the operations of SMEs particularly, the plastic firms in Anambra State pose a significant threat to sustainable development. The activities of SMEs are often characterized by inadequate waste management, pollution and non-compliance with environmental regulations. Furthermore, the lack of adoption of green governance practices and sustainable business model by these SME exacerbate environmental problems and therefore undermines their long-term viability. Hence, this study aims to investigate the relationship between green governance and sustainability of SMEs in Anambra State, using selected Plastic Manufacturing Firms in the state as the study area.

Objective of the study

The broad objective of the study is to investigate the effect of green governance on sustainability of Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

Original Article

(i) Determine the effect of green human resources management (GHRM) on employee retention in Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

(ii) Ascertain the effect of environmental stewardship on eco-innovation in Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

(i) What is the effect of green human resources practices on employee retention in Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?

(ii) How does environmental stewardship affect eco-innovation in Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the objective and strengthen the analysis in the study:

(i) Green HRM does not have significant and positive effect on employee-on-employee retention in Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

(ii) Environmental stewardship does not have positive effect on eco-innovation in Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

The term "green governance" refers to the attainment of a clean and healthy environment, which serves as a framework that resolves conflicts between humans and nature by implementing a system of institutional regulations (Shaina and Bambag, 2022). Amandeep and Mishra (2019) define Green Governance as encompassing collective and predetermined actions geared towards ensuring the safety, prosperity, stability, and continuity of sustainable development. In essence, green governance guarantees that decision-making prioritizes sustainable practices across economic, social, and environmental dimensions (Mahmood and Orazalin, 2017; Sharina and Bombag, 2022). Green governance, involves the development and implementation of policies, regulations, and practices aimed at promoting sustainability and environmentally friendly business practices that are crucial for mitigating the negative effects of economic activities (Oyedepo, 2022). Green governance contributes to global sustainability by fostering collaboration and decentralization among governmental, non-governmental organizations, and businesses, thereby supporting a distributed approach to sustainable practices (Amandeep and Mishra, 2019). Furthermore, effective green governance plays a crucial role in aligning corporate governance with common goals and objectives. Achieving the incorporation of green governance principles into real-world practices and establishing the link between environmental governance and sustainable development relies solely on sound decision-making processes (Amandeep and Mishra, 2019).

Sustainability is an important aspect of development with growing awareness among people in developing countries as climate change and environmental disasters are major threats to the planet and demands more attention through policies that connect the environment, economic and society (Raziq, Mahmood and Khan (2024). Many SMEs, especially those in developing countries, lack the awareness of environmental issues and the resources needed to implement green practices such limited access to information, training and development-, and financing, hinders their ability to adopt sustainable measures (Raziq, Mahmood & Khan

Original Article

,2024). Furthermore, technological Constraints: SMEs may lack access to affordable green technologies or lack the technical expertise to implement them effectively. This technological barrier hinders their ability to adopt sustainable practices. Access to Finance: Financing green initiatives can be challenging for SMEs, particularly startups and micro-enterprises, which often face difficulties accessing capital Compliance costs, administrative burdens, and the risk of penalties, pose significant challenges for small businesses (Min, Jayaram, & Xu, 2018).

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM)

GHRM stands for Green Human Resource Management, which involves incorporating eco-friendly practices into HRM procedures. GHRM aligns with environmentally conscious aspect of HRM, aiming to achieve favorable environmental outcomes within HRM functions (Adeyefa et. al,2023). Implementing GHRM practices could be deemed a more appropriate framework, considering that they yield impacts on both organizational functioning and the environment. Furthermore, several studies have discovered a link between the adoption of GHRM practices and the successful implementation of environmentally sustainable procedures. Adeyefa et. al, (2023) has outlined the most effective GHRM practices aimed at fostering employee commitment to an organization. Furthermore, green practices are helpful to improve the SMEs image, encourage self-confidence among workers, increase productivity, reduce costs, minimize waste, and save time (Adeyefa et. al, 2023).

Green Human Resources Management (GHRM) practice is described as a series of practices, processes and policies that encourage the sustainable behavior of an employee of an organization in terms of generating an organization resource-efficient, socially responsible and as well as environmentally sensitive (Zubair and Khan, 2018). Kumar et.al. (2023), asserts that the objective of GHRM is to motivate the workers and create a sense of pride in them as part of sustainable development. Further, it helps to create brand images of a company, upgrade the morale of the workers, retain talent and finally help to attract competitive employees. Therefore, GHRM have both organizational and environmental impact and the most effective GHRM practices include;

Recruitment and Selection: Recruitment specifically refers to the method of discovering and inviting potential candidates (within and outside of the establishment) into an evaluation for job considerations. On the other hand, selection is a streamlining process in which organizations decide which suitable candidate will join or will not the organization. It has been argued that for organizations to establish and sustain competitive advantage, it is essential to select the right candidate (Adeyefa et. al,2023).

Green Training and Development (GTD): GTD includes work practices for employees to enhance waste reduction, resource efficiency, energy conservation, and alleviate environmental degradation caused by SMEs operations (Ullah, 2017). GTD helps teach employees about green initiatives and skills concerning eco-friendly issues (Adeyefa et. al, 2023). Furthermore, this program **GTD** may also be effective in instilling a sense of interest in environmental problem-solving skills amongst employees. The flow of knowledge regarding green policies can substantially impact environment-related performance in SMEs and also create a sense of environmental consciousness (Deepika and Karpagam, 2016). Furthermore, it is possible for companies that invest in training and development of their employees to expect profits and yield for their venture.

Green performance and appraisal (GPA): GPA are concerned with assessing workers' performance within the operating system of an organization (Guiyaoetal.,2017). For better efficiency, firms ought to grant higher regard for the organization's goals when determining a technique to implement green performance. Adopting

Original Article

and implementing a GP standard is necessary to guarantee the performance of employees in accomplishing organizational goals (Adeyefa et. al,2023). In addition, employees must be tested for their success with regard to the SMEs green goal.

Green pay and reward (GPR): Ahmad, (2015), describes GPR as the processes that appreciate the efforts and performance of employees. Adeyefa et al. (2023) aver that GPR is a combination of monetary and non-monetary incentives designed to attract and motivate workers to contribute to SMEs goals. Green pay and rewards commonly involve salary, wages, or other incentives that can be used in support of improving the environmental initiatives of the business entity. Rewards are powerful and significant tools to affect an individual's interests and behavior. A green reward scheme serves as a tool to inspire all levels of staff into retention (Adeyefa et al. 2023). Furthermore, Staff can be given money or other forms of incentives such as honours, awards, and praises to ensure employee attention and dedication to their duties.

Employee green relations (EGR): EGR is the practice that regulates and controls the behaviours of supervisors towards employees and promotes a healthy and harmonious employee-employer relationship. Employees can be included in environmental management practices that encourage them to support pollution reduction and identify opportunities to participate in environmentally friendly actions (Adeyefa et al. 2023). Engaging in EGR could involve planning orientation programs that help to integrate new employees into a culture of green consciousness (Ullah,2017). Deepika and Karpagam (2016) emphasize those employees' contributions towards green initiatives will likely increase the effectiveness of green management practices. Furthermore, it is important to cultivate an environment that encourages employees to support green initiatives through intentional actions and decisions.

Green Health & Safety (GHS): Iheanacho and Ebitu, (2016), see GHS policies as a system concerned with the proper management of the environment through efforts that seek to protect employees and involved persons from having their health and safety threatened by an organization's operations, products, and services. Management staff must become advocates for safety plans, and employees allowed to offer suggestions to improve workplace safety (Adeyefa et al. 2023). When their welfare is deemed important to the organization, employees are more likely to find fulfillment in their job and exercise great performance. Pham,Tučková & Jabbour (2019), emphasize that employees are more likely to willingly engage in green initiatives if they perceive support and benefits arising from engaging in green practices.

Environmental Stewardship

Stewardship: Stewardship actions include combinations of approaches, activities, behaviours and technologies that are applied to protect, restore or sustainably use the environment as a medium to improve on business processes and gain innovative advantage (Bennett et al., 2018). Environmental stewardship is an action that embraces and balances the need for various groups while ensuring that natural resources are consistently conserved and used responsibly. From a more appropriate standpoint, Olubodun and Agbaje, (2021) assert that environmental stewardship is the responsible utilization (including conservation) of natural resources in a manner that comprehensively considers the interests of society, future generations, and other species, alongside private needs, while acknowledging significant accountability to society. Environmental stewardship is also defined as the responsible management of natural resources and ecosystems to ensure their sustainability for present and future generations (UNEP, 2022). It involves taking proactive measures to minimize environmental

Original Article

impact, promote biodiversity, and address climate change (EPA, 2022). Smith and Toffel (2021) state that SMEs play a significant role in environmental stewardship, and their governance practices have a direct impact on their environmental performance. SMEs often face unique challenges in implementing environmental initiatives, but effective governance can facilitate the integration of sustainability principles into their operations (Lee and Klassen, 2020).

Environmental stewardship in SMEs is implemented through a combination of initiatives such as adopting eco-friendly technologies, reducing waste generation, and implementing sustainable supply chain practices (Wu, Hu, and Zhang, 2021). Wu et al. (2021), suggest that SMEs can enhance their environmental stewardship by integrating sustainability principles into their business operations, fostering a culture of environmental responsibility among employees, and engaging with stakeholders to address environmental concerns. It involves companies going beyond rationality in their environmental actions (Olubodun and Agbaje, 2021). Furthermore, maintaining environmental stewardship represents a collective responsibility toward the environment, reflected in an organization's policies, procedures, and actions regarding relationships with employees and customers. Stewardship actions encompass a blend of approaches, activities, behaviors, and technologies utilized to safeguard, restore, or sustainably utilize the environment as a means to enhance business processes and achieve innovative advantages (Bennett et al., 2018). Wu, Wang Philipsen and Fang (2023) posit that firms are driven by environmental regulations to distribute a part of their input (labour, capital) to pollution reduction, promoting environmental benefits to society and fostering business sustainability.

Employee Retention

Adeyefa et. al (2023) described employee retention as a commitment to remain in an exchange or business with a specific company. The primary goal of any establishment is to deliberately cultivate conditions that facilitate the long-term retention of its workforce, as noted by Nyamekye (2012). Norah (2016) suggests that employee retention is driven by various factors that require efficient management. These factors comprise work benefits, salary, career advancement, and the organization itself, all of which need to be effectively managed for retention. Ann (2017) concurs that the primary objective of retention is to prevent the loss of skilled employees, as this could potentially diminish the productivity and profitability of the company.

Organizational leaders appear to be increasingly cognizant that retaining an employee is often more cost-effective than recruiting a replacement (Zahoor and Ijaz, 2015). Hence, it is customary to employ a range of methods that support the retention of a dynamic workforce while also fulfilling operational requirements. Significantly, workplace stress can exacerbate interpersonal conflicts and raise the probability of employees taking leave or being absent from work (Ann, 2017). Hence, Ann (2017) advocate for managers to closely monitor their workers as a means of minimizing any indications of discontentment and stress. Several factors that are responsible for employee retention include; compensation and recognition for work, opportunities for engaging tasks, avenues for learning and advancement, favorable working conditions, positive relationships among colleagues, a harmonious work-life balance, and effective communication within the organization (Das and Baruah ,2013).

Coetzer, et. al (2019), posit that employee retention strategies are aimed at preserving talented individuals who are very scare to attract and retain. Furthermore, having such skilled employees is advantageous for any organization since they actively participate in daily operations, providing essential skills, capacity, and

Original Article

knowledge that facilitate the achievement of organizational goals. Preserving talented employees within the organization not only safeguards institutional knowledge but also mitigates the costs typically involved in recruiting and training new staff (Grace and Daniel, 2022). Furthermore, owing to their experience, long-term employees tend to be inherently more productive compared to new hires, regardless of the competency and potential the new hire may bring to the position (Grace and Daniel, 2022). Hassan, et. al (2020) suggest that ensuring employee retention involves, addressing their diverse and individual needs, which vary from person to person. Managers need to skillfully integrate multiple practices such as sufficient compensation, flexible work schedules, servant leadership approach and fair recruitment practices to build an environment where employees, with varying needs, opt to remain with the organization (Yousuf, & Siddiqui, 2019; Grace and Daniel, 2022).

Eco-Innovation

Lesakova, (2019), describes eco-innovation as the development of new products and processes that provide value to customers and businesses, while also significantly reducing environmental impacts. Chukwuka and Nwomiko (2018), posit that eco-innovation encompasses novel products and processes that deliver value to both customers and businesses while substantially reducing environmental impacts. Eco-innovation encompasses all environmental improvements across the whole product life cycle, concerning the way they are designed, produced, used, reused, and recycled and thus, it stands as a potent tool that harmonizes diminished adverse effect on the environment with a favorable impact on the economy and society (Lobzhanidz, Mikiashvili, 2017). Furthermore, it involves the process of creative destruction, wherein outdated practices and capabilities are replaced with new ones.

Theoretical Framework

Several theories about green governance practices support the concept of sustainability, but the theories underpinning this study are: agency theory (Jensen and Meckling, 1976 resource-based view theory by Jay Barney in (1991) and Stakeholders Theory by Freeman (1984).

The resource-based view (RBV) of the firm was primarily developed by Jay Barney in (1991). His work in 1980s and 1990s established the RBV as a key theory in strategic management, emphasizing that a firm's unique resources and capabilities are central to achieving a competitive advantage.

Agency theory is a principle that examines the relationship between principals (such as shareholders) and agents (such as executives or managers) in organizations. It focuses on the conflicts of interest that may arise when the goals of principals (who delegate authority to agents to act on their behalf) and agents diverge. The theory explores how these conflicts can potentially lead to agency costs such as monitoring costs, bonding costs, and residual losses and how various mechanisms, and corporate governance structures can mitigate these conflicts to align the interests of both parties.

The assumptions of stakeholder theory under business sustainability perspective, is that the firm is a system whose survival depends on its surroundings. The purpose of the firm is not only to create and distribute value between the shareholders, as agency theory posits, but also to provide value to other stakeholders and generate sustainable wealth over time. As collaborations between stakeholders contribute to creating added value, and value creation plays a part in the firm's long-term survival, stakeholders are essential for the sustainability of the firm.

Original Article

However, the adoption of best practices that encourage investment in employee will create core competencies that have value, very scarce and rare for firms to earn competitive advantage that increases organizational performance. The best practices approach therefore, supports resource-base-view of the firm where a firm's internal resources are optimally enhanced to motivate employees, increase efficiency and create competitive advantage that is sustainable.

Empirical Review

Awaisu, Haslindar and Dayana (2024) examined environmental governance as a driver of green eco-innovation capacity and firm value creation in Nigeria. Data were collected from 74 Companies traded in the Nigeria stock Exchange (NSX) for year 2012-2021. The systematic finding of the study focuses in resenting the dimensions of environmental governance that drives capacities in green innovation and firm value creation, and those that are not. Findings indicates that the more a company recognizes the importance of governance, environment and economic governance, the higher the tendencies for companies to have capacities in green innovation. The findings of the study have significant influence on green innovation research, because they display the value and capability of environmental governance in driving green innovation capacity and firm value creation. The study recommends that green innovation capacities are driven by environment and governance densities, while firm value creations are driven by social and environmental densities in the Nigerian capital market.

Raziq, Mahmood and Khan. (2024). Investigated the barriers to adoption of environmental sustainability small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan. The objective of the study is to explore the specific internal and external factors for environmental sustainability. Purposive sampling techniques were used to select a sample size of 30 SMEs. In-depth quantitative interviews were conducted using a semi-structured questionnaire. Findings of the study revealed that lack of finance and education are major barriers to recognizing and addressing environmental sustainability issues, along with the lack of government support and regulations to ensure compliance with environmental safety laws, hence leading to low concern for sustainability practices among SMEs.

Wang, Ur Rehman, Xu, Amjad and Ur Rehman (2023) investigated Green Corporate Governance, Green Finance and sustainable performance in Chinese SMEs, taking into account the perspectives of Agency theory and Stakeholder's theory. Data were collected through a questionnaire survey of 314 employees working in SMEs in China. Data were analysed using Smart DLS 4 and SPSS. Finding indicates that green corporate governance and green finance have a significant impact on corporate social responsibility, which inturn positively affects sustainability performance. The study recommends that green governance, green finance and sustainable performance have significant implication for policy-makers and managers interested in promoting sustainable development.

Enyi, Kwahar, Hanmaikyur, Adudu and Jato (2023) examined the effect of green entrepreneurship practices on the sustainability of manufacturing SMEs in North Central, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research method, using questionnaire administration for data generation from a sample of 327 employees of selected manufacturing SMEs in North Central Nigeria, Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statics. T-test and P-value from regression analysis using SPSS version 25.0 was used for testing the hypothesis. Findings revealed that green entrepreneurial initiatives have significant and positive effect on sustainability of manufacturing SMEs. The study recommends that among others that management of manufacturing SMEs

Original Article

should continually attend to green entrepreneurial initiatives as an enabler, as it will enhance their business undertaking towards achieving innovative products that are eco-friendly through natural resources related and keep the firm in a better sustainable position.

Kumar, Jamali, Agyei and Lourens (2023) investigated the practice of green HRM on employee retention and sustainability of corporate business in India. Senior managers and HR experts were interviewed; partial least sequence (PLS) structures equation modeling was used for the analysis of data. Smart PLS 3.0 software was used since the study aims to anticipate association. Findings revealed that training, employee motivation, recruitment and compensation are the most supreme human dimension that commit to the up gradation in the implementation of employee sustainable management practices. The study recommends that staff members should have the knowledge and resources necessary to successfully implement green HRM practice and they should offer training and development opportunities.

Audu, Odekina and Obiora (2023) Carried research on Green HRM and employee retention in Hospitality Industry in Kogi, Nigeria, to examine how Hospitality in Kogi State utilize green recruitment, training and green compensation towards retaining their employees. The study adopted a descriptive research survey design and complete enumeration method. Respondents were reached through questionnaire. The respondents comprise those at the management level, supervisors, senior or junior categories. Data were analyzed using with both descriptive and inferential statistics. Hypotheses were tested using multiple regressions. Findings indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between green human resources practices and employees' retention in the hospitality industry in Kogi State, Nigeria. Their study recommends that the management of hospitality firms in Kogi State should not only focus on green recruitment, training and compensation but should also ensure that these practices are integrated into their operational manual and company human resources policy.

Aremu and Adepoju (2022) examined green human resources management and employee retention in foods and Beverages Industry in Nigeria. Purposive Random Sampling technique was used to select the food and beverages Industries located in Southwest, Nigeria. A simple random sampling method was used to select a sample size of three hundred and forty-seven (347) respondents. The research instrument used to collect data was a closed ended questionnaire. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Findings revealed that employee socialization, green ethic management, green reward system, green health and safety and green remote staffing have significant relationship with employee retention. The study recommends that the management of food and beverage companies should adopt and implement green HRM practices.

Imevbore (2020) examined environmental stewardship in the upstream oil and gas sector from two perspectives: The realities of the industry-environment interactions based on the status of pollution; and biodiversity conservation and biodiversity conservation perspectives: The roles and performances of key players in the industry including the, oil and gas operators, communities and other government agencies. Data from recent ground trusting and sampling from petroleum concentration in soil, eater and sediments were used. Findings show that the use and protection of the Nigerian environment within and around many upstream oil and gas operations is currently less than desirable. Oil pollution is still extensive while biodiversity conservation is minimal. The study concludes that environmental stewardship will remain a myth until a more cooperative and

Original Article

streamlined multi-stakeholder approach is pursued together with veritable and sustainable poverty alleviation initiatives in the region.

Olubodum and Agbja (2021) examined the relationship between environmental stewardship and business sustainability in small and medium packaged water in Nigeria. Research survey was used in which environmental stewardship proxy as community engagement activities on business sustainability which is viewed along three dimensional (economic, social and environmental) balances in the questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics while multiple regressions was employed to determine the effect of environmental stewardship on business sustainability. The results show that there is positive significant effect of environmental stewardship on business sustainability. The study concludes that recycling and waste reduction and management actions will enhance business sustainability.

Gap in Literature

There exists methodological gap, variable gap, geographical gap and periodic gap. There is limited research on the present study. From the reviewed studies, the methodologies, variables, location and time are different from that of the present study. Therefore, this study sought to bridge these gaps.

Research Design

The study made use of descriptive survey design to facilitate generalizability research findings to the entire population of interest among reasons. The population of the study comprised the staff of the seven (7) registered Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State, cutting across the industrial zones of Awka, Onitsha and Nnewi. A total of 243 staff strength was identified for the Manufacturers' Association of Nigeria (MAN) Fact Book (2024) as the study's population. From the population, 151 employees were determined as the sample, using Taro Yamani's formula for determining sample size from a finite population.

Model Specification

The Study examines the effect of green governance on sustainability plastic manufacturing firms in the SMEs sector in Anambra State. Owing to the fact that business sustainability was decomposed into employee retention and eco-innovation, two distinct models were specified as follows:

The First Model

$$ER = f(\text{GRHM}) \quad (i)$$

Econometrically stated, it becomes:

$$ER = \alpha_0 + \alpha \text{GRHM} + \mu_t \quad (ii)$$

Where:

ER = Employee retention

α_0 = The intercept

μ_t = The stochastic error term

GRHM= Green human resource management

α = coefficient of independent variable

Expected sign of the coefficient or *a priori*

$\alpha > 0$.

Second Model:

$$EI = f(\text{ESW}) \quad (i)$$

Stated econometrically, it becomes:

$$EI = \alpha_0 + \alpha \text{ESW} + \mu_t \quad (ii)$$

Original Article

Where:

EI = Eco-Innovation

α_0 = The intercept

μ_t = The stochastic error term

ESW = Environmental Stewardship

α = The coefficient of independent variable

Expected sign of the coefficient or *a priori*

$\alpha > 0$

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Research Question

Research Question One:

Research question one wants to ascertain whether there is any relationship between green human resource management practice and employee retention. Accordingly, the opinion of the respondents is presented in Table 2 in Likert Scale format.

Table 2: Green Human Resource Management Practices and Employee Retention in Plastic Firms in Anambra State

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Likert Scale Option					Total
		SA	A	D	SD	UND	
1.	Green Human Resources Management (GHRM) practice is a series of practices, processes and policies that encourage the sustainable behavior of an employee through training and development which results to profit and yields for the venture.	45 (31.0)	60 (41.2)	20 (13.8)	15 (10.3)	5 (3.4)	145 (100)
2.	It is environmentally friendly strategies that enhance environmental sustainability and retention of employees	50 (34.5)	67 (46.2)	15 (10.3)	10 (6.9)	3 (2.1)	145 (100)
3.	GHRM practice by organizations reduce turnover rate of employees and stop them from leaving the organization.	40 (25.6)	70 (48.3)	18 (12.4)	10 (6.9)	7 (4.8)	145 (100)
4.	GHRM practices aimed at fostering employee commitment to an organization.	55 (37.9)	63 (43.4)	16 (11.0)	6 (4.1)	5 (3.4)	145 (100)
5.	It has helpful in boost my firm’s image, encourage self-confidence among workers, increase productivity, reduce costs, minimize waste, and save time.	49 (33.8)	60 (41.2)	20 (13.8)	10 (6.9)	6 (4.6)	145 (100)
Total		239	320	89	51	26	725
Percentage of Total		(33.0)	(44.1)	(12.3)	(7.0)	(3.6)	(100)

Note: (SA = Strongly agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree; SD = Strongly disagree and UND = Undecided).

Original Article

The analysis of the research question in Table 2 shows that on the average 33 percent of the respondents strongly agreed with all the statement of the items, 44.1 percent merely agreed, 12.3 percent of the respondents disagreed, 7 percent of them strongly disagreed, while 3.6 percent of them were undecided on all the issues raised in the section.

Research Question Two:

This research question wants to determine whether there is any relationship between environmental stewardship and eco-innovation in plastic manufacturing firms, Anambra State. Accordingly, the opinion of the respondents is presented in Table 3 in Likert Scale format.

Table 3: Environmental Stewardship and Eco-innovation in Plastic Firms in Anambra State,

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Likert Scale Option					Total
		SA	A	D	SD	UN D	
1.	Environmental stewardship entails taking action to accommodate and balance the requirements of various groups, while also ensuring the consistent conservation and responsible use of natural resources.	45 (31.0)	60 (41.4)	20 (13.8)	15 (10.3)	5 (3.4)	145 (100)
2.	It is a blend of approaches, activities, behaviors, and technologies utilized to safeguard, restore, or sustainably utilize the environment as a means to enhance business processes and achieve innovative advantages.	57 (39.3)	62 (42.8)	20 (13.8)	3 (2.1)	3 (2.1)	145 (100)
3.	It is implemented through adopting eco-friendly technologies that reduces waste generation, and implementing sustainable supply chain practices.	49 (33.8)	70 (48.3)	18 (12.4)	5 (3.4)	3 (2.1)	145 (100)
4.	It is expected to represents a collective responsibility toward the environment, reflected in an organization's policies, procedures, and actions regarding relationships with employees and customers.	50 (34.5)	65 (44.8)	20 (13.8)	5 (3.4)	5 (3.4)	145 (100)
5.	It provides value to customers and businesses, while also significantly reducing environmental impacts.	59 (40.7)	67 (46.2)	13 (9.0)	4 (2.8)	2 (1.4)	145 (100)
Total		260	324	91	32	18	725
Percentage of Total		(35.9)	(44.7)	(12.6)	(4.4)	(2.5)	(100)

Note: (SA = Strongly agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree; SD = Strongly disagree and UND = Undecided).

Original Article

From Table 3, 35.9 percent of the respondents on the average strongly agreed to a very large extent that environmental stewardship can lead to sustainability of firms in the plastic firms in Anambra State, 47.7 percent equally agreed but not to a very large extent, 12.6 percent of them strongly disagreed, 4.4 percent disagree that environmental stewardship has effect on eco-innovation of Plastic firms in Anambra State, whereas 2.5percent of the respondents were undecided.

Table 4: Dependent Variable: Sustainability of Firms in the SMEs Sector

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Likert Scale Options					Total
		VGE	GE	ME	LE	VLE	
1.	To what extent do you agree that green HRM practices can lead to employee retention in Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State?	40 (25.6)	70 (48.3)	18 (12.4)	10 (6.9)	7 (4.8)	145 (100)
2.	To what extent do you agree that environmental stewardship can lead to Eco-innovation in Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State?	55 (37.9)	63 (43.4)	16 (11.0)	6 (4.1)	5 (3.4)	145 (100)
Total		95	133	34	16	12	290
Percentage of Total		(32.8)	(45.9)	(11.7)	(5.5)	(4.1)	(100)

Note: (VGE = Very great extent; GE = Great extent; ME = Moderate extent; LE = Little extent and VLE = Very little extent).

From Table 4, 32.8 percent of the respondents on the average agreed to a very large extent that green governance can lead to sustainability of firms in the MSMEs sector in Anambra State, 45.9 percent equally agreed but not to a very large extent, 11.7 percent of them agreed to a moderate extent, 5.5 percent that green governance can lead to sustainability of plastic firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 5(a): Correlation Analysis

Correlation Matrix

Variables			Employee Retention	Green Human Resource Management
Employee Retention	Pearson Correlation		1	.507**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000
	N		145	145
Green Human Resource Management	Pearson Correlation		.507**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N		145	145

** Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Original Article

Table 5(b): Correlation Analysis

Correlation Matrix

Variables		Environmental Stewardship	Eco-Innovation
Environmental Stewardship	Pearson Correlation	1	.629**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	145	145
Eco-Innovation	Pearson Correlation	.629**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	145	145

** Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 6: Analysis of Variance for Model I ANOVA^b

Source of Variation	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig.
Regression	4	120.701	30.175	13.963	.000 ^a
Residual	20	97.235	2.161		
Total	24	217.936			

a. Predictor: (constant), and green human resource management

b. Dependent variable: Employee Retention

Table 6 shows that F-Statistic of 13.963 is statistically significant because $P_{0.000}$ is less than $p < 0.05$.

Table 7: Summary of Regression Results I

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson Stat.
I	0.497	0.401	0.422	0.39875	2.001

a. Predictor: (constant), and green human resource management.

The regression results presented in Table 7 showed that regression coefficient represented by ‘R’ in the table with a value of .497 shows that 49.7 percent relationship exists between the dependent and independent variable. Similarly, the coefficient of determination represented by ‘R²’ in table shows that 40.1 percent variation in dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable.

Original Article

Table 8: Coefficients, t-values and Significance Levels

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
1(Constant)	.175	.205	-	-.308	.302
Green HRM	.262	.075	.609	10.161	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employees Retention

Table 9: Analysis of Variance for Model II ANOVA^b

Source of Variation	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig.
Regression	4	110.809	27.702	6.229	.000 ^a
Residual	20	88.931	4.447		
Total	24	199.740			

a. Predictor: (constant), environmental stewardship

b. Dependent variable: Eco-Innovation

Table 9 shows that F-Statistic of 6.229 is statistically significant because $P_{0.000}$ is less than $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the model is valid for prediction.

Table 10: Summary of Regression Results II

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson Stat.
I	.598	.506	.471	.39785	.907

a. Predictor: (constant), environmental stewardship

Table 10 shows that regression coefficient with a value of .598 is an indication that 59.8 percent relationship exists between the dependent and independent variables. Similarly, the coefficient of determination represented by 'R²' in the table with a value of .506 shows that 50.6 percent variation in dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable.

Table 11: Coefficients, t-values and Significance Levels

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
1(Constant)	.164	.201	-	-.405	.421
Environmental stewardship	.251	.068	.611	4.265	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Eco-innovation

Original Article

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

1. H₀: Green human resource management practices does not have significant and positive effect on employees' retention in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State.

H₁: Green human resource management practices have significant and positive effect on employees' retention in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State.

The coefficient of green human resource management represented by α in the model with a value of .609 in Table 8 shows that when the variable is increased by one unit, employee's retention will increase by 60.9 percent. The t-value of 10.161 and its corresponding significance level of .000 are indications that the coefficient is significant and positive because $P_{.000}$ less than $p < 0.05$. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative which suggests that green human resource management practices have significant and positive effect on employees' retention in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State was accepted.

Hypothesis Two:

2. H₀: Environmental stewardship does not have significant and positive effect on eco-innovation in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State.

H₁: Environmental stewardship has significant and positive effect on eco-innovation in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State.

The coefficient of environmental stewardship represented by α in the model with a value of .611 in Table 11, shows that when the variable is increased by one-unit, eco-innovation will increase by 61.1 percent. The t-value of 4.265 and its corresponding significance level of .000 are indications that the coefficient is significant because $P_{0.000}$ is less than $P < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative which suggests that environmental stewardship has significant and positive effect on eco-innovation in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State was accepted.

Interpretation of Results

As could be seen from Table 4.8, the coefficient of green human resource management practice is .609 and it means that when it is increased by unit, employee retention which moderates firm sustainability in the SMEs will increase by 60.9 percent, if other factors in the model are held constant. The t-value of 10.161 and its corresponding significance level of .000 are indications that the coefficient is significant because $P_{0.000}$ is less than $P \leq 0.05$. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative which suggests that green human resource management practice has significant and positive effect on employees' retention in SMEs in Anambra State accepted.

In the same vein, the coefficient of environmental stewardship which is .611 shows that if the coefficient is increased by one unit co-innovation which moderates sustainability of firms in MSMEs will increase by 61.1 percent if other variables are hold constant. Also, the t-value of 4.265 and its corresponding significance level of .000 are equally indications that the coefficient is significant and positive because $P_{0.000}$ less than $P \leq 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and we concluded that environment stewardship has significant and positive effect on eco-innovation in firms in MSMEs of Anambra State.

Discussion of Research Findings

The result of the first test of hypothesis showed that green human resource management practice has significant and positive effect on employee retention as a moderator of sustainability of firms in the SMEs sector in

Original Article

Anambra State. The result is consistent with that of Audu, Odekina and Obiora (2023) when they found from their study that there is a significant positive relationship between green human resource management practice and employee retention in the hospitality industries in Kogi State, Nigeria.

The result of the second test of hypothesis showed that environmental stewardship has significant and positive effect on eco-innovation of Plastic Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State. This result is consistent with that of Awaisu, Haslindar and Dayana (2024), who found from their study that there is a significant influence on green innovation research on environmental stewardship and the more company recognizes the importance of environment and economic governance, the higher the tendencies for companies to have capacities in green innovation.

Conclusion

The study concluded that green governance can lead to sustainability of Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State.

Green human resource management practice has significant and positive effect on employee retention of Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State. Consequently, Environmental stewardship has significant and positive effect on eco-innovation of Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State.

Recommendations:

The study recommends that:

1. Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State should ensure that their green governance policies/practices aim at achieving sustainability in their business operations.
2. The management needs to adopt Green Human Resource Management policies that could promote employee retention by combining several practices that aims address the different needs of employees, to ensure continuity of their workers in the organization. Managers should consider environmental governance as one of indispensable instruments to enhance eco-innovation activities as well as capacity building and value creation for their firm.

REFERENCES

- Adeyefa, A.E., Adedipe, A., Adebayo, I.N. & Adesuyan, A.J. (2023). Influence of Green Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Retention in the Hotel. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 12(1):114-130.
- Amandeep, N. and Akilesh (2019) Green governance – a stepping stone for sustainable development. *Think Indian Journal* vol.22(33):0971-1260.
- Amrutha, V., & Geetha, S. (2020). A systematic review on green human resource management: Implications for social sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.
- Ann S. A. (2017). What a Human Resources Management Best Practice Influence Employee Satisfaction and Job Retention in the Thai Hotel Industry. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 17(2), 175-199.

Original Article

- Aremu, M.A. & Adepinu, J. O. (2023). Green Human Resources management (GHRM) strategies: an approach to environmental sustainability in organization. *Journal of environmental sustainability*, vol. 12(4):245-260.
- Audu, S. Odekina, F. A. & Obioru, J. I. (2023) Green human resource management practices and employee retention Hospitality Industry, Kogi state, Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration, Policy and Governance Research*, vol. 1(1):59-69.
- Awaisu, A. S, Has, L & Doyana, M.B., (2024) Environmental governance as a driver of green innovation capability and firm value creation. *Journal of innovation and green policy*, vol.3(2):100-110.
- Baalouch, F. Ayadi, S.D. Hussainey, K. (2019) A study of the determinants of environmental disclosure quality: Evidence from French listed companies. *J. Manag. Gov.*, 23, 939–971.
- Bennett, N. J., Whitty, T. S., Finkbeiner, E., Pittman, J., Bassett, H., Geleich, S., & Allison, E.H. (2018). Environmental Stewardship: A Conceptual Review and Analytical Framework. *Ecological and the Environment*, vol.16(3):132-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-017-0993-2>
- Bikefe, G. G. and Daniel, C. O. (2022) Employee retention practices and the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *use as Transaction on Business and Economics* vol. 19:134 DOI: 10.37394/23207.2022.19.1.
- Brundtland, G.H (1987) *Our common future*, world commission on environment and development; University Press: Oxford, UK.
- Calza, F., Parmentola, A, & Tutore, I. (2017). Types of green innovations:Ways of implementation in a non-green industry. *Sustainability*, vol 9(8):1301. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9081301>.
- Chairina, C and Tjahjadi, B. (2023) “Green governance and sustainability Report quality: Moderating role of sustainability commitment in ASEAN Countries,” *Economies*. MDPI, vol/11(1):1-17.
- Chege S.M and Wang D. (2022) The influence of technology innovation on SME performance through environmental sustainability practices in Kenya. *Technol. Soc.* Vol.60:101-210.
- Chen, F. Ngniatedema, T. & Li, S. (2018) A cross-country comparison of green initiatives, green performance and financial performance. *Journal Management. Decission*. Vol.56:1008–1032.
- Chukwuka, E. J. and Nwomiko, U. N. (2018) Sustainability-Oriented Practices of Eco-Innovation, Eco-Commitment and Organizational Performance of a Developing Economy. *World Journal of Research and Review* vol.6(4):12-26.

Original Article

- Coetzer, A., Inma, C., Poisat, P., Redmond, J., & Standing, C. (2019) Does job embeddedness predict turnover intentions in SMEs? *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management, Vol.68* (2):340-361.
- Cooke, P. (2015) Green governance and green clusters: Regional & national policies for the climate change challenge of Central& Eastern Europe Open Innov. Technol. Mark J. Complex.vol11: 1-17.
- Dangelico, R.M. (2015). Improving firm environmental performance and reputation: *The role of employee green teams. Bus Strateg. Environ. 24, 735–749.*
- Das, B. L. & Baruah, M. (2013). “Employee Retention: A Literature Review”. *Journal of Business Management, 14* (2), 08-16.
- Deepika, R., &Karpagnam, V. (2016). A study on green HRM practices in an organization. *International Journal of applied Research, 2*(8): 425-429.
- Diri, T. V. (2021). Green human resources management and corporate sustainability of oil and gas producing companies in Rivers State. An unpublished dissertation in the department of management sciences. University Press.
- Enyi, L. A., Kwahar, N. Ph.D., Hanmaikyur, T.J. Ph.D., Adudu C. A and Jato, S. (2023) Green Entrepreneurial Practices and the Sustainability of Manufacturing SMES in North Central Nigeria *International Journal of Management Sciences* vol.11(2):107-129.
- EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency). (2022). What is environmental stewardship? Retrieved from <https://www.epa.gov/sustainability/what-environmental-stewardship>.
- Fatma, N., & Haleem, A (2023), Exploring the nexus of eco-innovation and sustainable development: A bibliometric review and analysis. *Sustainability, Vol.15*(16), 12281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151612281>.
- Gennari, F. and Salvioni, D. M. (2019). CSR committees on boards: The impact of the external country level factors. *Journal of Management Governance* (23): 759– 785.
- Genty, K.I., (2021), Green human resource practices and organisational sustainability. IGI Global. Doi:10.4018/978/1/7998-4522-5.ch001.
- Grace George Bikefe and Cross Ogohi Daniel (2022) Employee Retention Practices and the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *Wseas Transaction on Business and Economics* vol. 19:134 DOI: 10.37394/23207.2022.19.134

Original Article

- Hassan, M. M., Jambulingam, M., Alagas, E. N., Uzir, M. U. H., & Halibuts, H. A. (2020) Necessities and ways of combating dissatisfactions at workplaces against the Job. *Global Business Review*, 0972150920926966
- Hussain, N., Rigoni, U., Orij, R. P. (2018). Corporate governance and sustainability performance: Analysis of triple bottom line performance. *J. Bus. Ethics* 149, 411–432.
- Iheanacho, M. U and Ebuti E.T. (2016) Effect of industrial safety and health on employees' job performance in selected cement companies in Cross river State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, vol.4(3):49-56.
- Janis et al. (2017). Green Governance Principles in The Development Of Environmental Education Infrastructure. *Latvia University of Agriculture*, 1(44), 256-266.
- Khan, N. (2019). Handbook of research on environmental policies for management and public safety. IGI Global.
- Kiefer C.P. Del Rio Gonzalez P. and Carrillo-Hermosilla J. (2019) Drivers and barriers of eco-innovation types for sustainable transitions: A quantitative perspective. *Bus. Strategy Environ.* Vol.28:155–172.
- Kiru, S. (2024) Determining Factors of Ecoinnovation Adoption: An Empirical Study of Micro and Small Enterprises in Johannesburg, South Africa: *Global Business Review*:1–20.
- Koirala S (2019) SMEs: Key drivers of green and inclusive growth; OECD green growth papers. No.03; OECD Publishing: Paris, France.
- Kraus P. Stokes P. Cooper S.C. Liu, Y. Moore N. Britzelmaier B and. Tarba S. (2020) Cultural antecedents of sustainability and regional economic development-A study of SME 'Mittelstand' Firms in Baden-Württemberg (Germany). *Entrep. Reg. Dev.* Vol. 32, 629–653.
- Kumar, M, & Sharan, V.D (2023). Role of Green Human Resource Management Practices on sustainable performance. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*.
- Kundurpi, A. Westman, L. Luederitz, C. Burch, S. and Mercado, A.(2021), Navigating between adaptation and transformation: How intermediaries support businesses in sustainability transitions. *J. Clean. Prod.* Vol. 283:125-366.
- Kundurpi, A. Westman, L. Luederitz, C. Burch, S. and Mercado, A.(2021), Navigating between adaptation and transformation: How intermediaries support businesses in sustainability transitions. *J. Clean. Prod.* Vol. 283:125-366.

Original Article

- Lars, K. Dirk S & Willem, S. (2021): A model of long-term value creation, *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, ISSN: (Print) (Online) *Journal homepage: <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/tsfi20>*
- Laura, R. Raquel, I. Luis, M. R. and Julio, N (2024) The use and drivers of organisational eco-innovation in European SMEs. *Research in international business and finance*, Vol. 70 Part A 102297.
- Lee, J., & Klassen, R. (2020). Governance and environmental stewardship: The role of boards of directors in SMEs. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 165(3), 549-563.
- Lesakova, L. (2019) Small and Medium Enterprises and Eco-Innovations: Empirical Study of Slovak SME's. *Marketing and Management of Innovations*, vol.3, 89-97. <http://doi.org/10.21272/mmi.2019.3-07>.
- Li, S., Ngniatedema, T., Chen, F. (2017). Understanding the impact of green initiatives and green performance on financial performance in the US. *Bus. Strateg. Environ.* 26, 776–790.
- Lobzhanidze, N., Mikiashvili, N. (2017). Green Innovations and Economic Policy in Small Economies. *Forum Scientiae Oeconomia* 5(2), 29-40.
- Martins A, Branco M.C, Melo P.N and Machado C. (2022) Sustainability in small and medium-sized enterprises: A systematic literature review and future research agenda. *Sustainability*. Vol.14:6493. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14116493>.
- Mayer (2018). *Prosperity: Better business makes the greater good*. oxford: Oxford university press.
- Mayer (2018). *Prosperity: Better business makes the greater good*: Oxford university press.
- Min, H., Jayaram, J., & Xu, L. (2018). The impact of regulatory pressures and environmental dynamism on green product innovation and firm performance: The moderating effect of environmental management capabilities. *Journal of Business Research*, 85, 32-45.
- Mousa, S. K., & Othman, M. (2020). The impact of green human resource management practices on sustainable performance in healthcare organisations: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 243, 118595.
- Muhammad, A. Abdul, H and Khatijah, O. (2022) Drivers of multiple eco-innovations and the impact on sustainable competitive advantage: evidence from manufacturing SMEs in Egypt. *International Journal of Innovation Science* Vol. 14(1):40-61.
- Norah S., Susan W. & Gichuhi A. W. (2016). Effects of Job Promotion on Employee Retention in Hotels in Kenya. *Strategic Journal of Business and Change Management*, 3 (4), 956-972.

Original Article

- Nwabuzor N. (2018) Exploring employee retention strategies in the U.S. Hotel Industry. Doctoral study submitted in partial fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Business Administration, Walden University.
- Nyamekye, F. (2012). Impact of Motivation on Employee Retention: A Case Study of Standard Chartered Bank Ghana Limited. Unpublished Master's Dissertation. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology.
- Obasi, I.N. (2000). Research Methodology in Political Science: Enugu: Academic Publishing Company.
- OECD (2008). Eco –innovation policies in the United States, environmental directorate, OECD. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.porg/united states/44247543>.
- Olubodun, I. E and Agbaje, Y. T. (2021) Environmental stewardship and strategy for business sustainability: Evidence from small and medium packaged water enterprises in Nigeria Management and Economics Review Volume 6, Issue 1:06-02.
- Olufemi., O. O., Osifalujo, B.B., and Ogunwede J. K. (2023) Stakeholders conflicting interest and approach for harmonization for business sustainability: Evidence from limited Liability Companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in social Sciences (IJISS) Vol. 7(9):21-33*.
- Onuoha, C., Daferighe, E.E, Etim, O. E. and Onuoha, J.C (2023) Green board committee and profitability of publicly Traded Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria GSJ: Volume 11, Issue 4, Online: ISSN 2320-9186. www.globalscientificjournal.com.
- Oyedepo, S.O. (2022) “Energy and sustainable development in Nigeria: the way forward, Energy, sustain. Soc., vol. 2(1):1-7.
- Pavol, K and Katarina, J. (2021) Eco-innovation a tool to support sustainable development and increased the competitiveness of enterprises: globalization and socio-economic consequences. SHS web conference 129, 05005.
- Pham, N.T., Tučková, Z. &Jabbour, C.J.C. (2019). Greening the Hospitality Industry: How do Green Human Resource Management Practices Influence Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Hotels? A Mixed-Methods Study. *Tourism Management*, 72, 386-399.
- Rao, S., & Chandra Mouli, S. (2017). Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) in IT Companies: Environmentally sustainable policies. *International Research Journal of Management Science & Technology*, 431-442.

Original Article

- Raziq a.I, Mahmood T. & Khan M. R. (2024). Investigated on Barriers to adoption of environmental sustainability small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan: A quantitative study. *PLoS ONE* Vol. 19(5): e0298580.
- Ruyter, K., Jong, A., &Wetzels, M. (2009). Antecedents and consequences of environmental stewardship in boundary-spanning B2B teams. *Journal of the Academic. Marketing Sciences*, 37, 470-487. doi 10.1007/s11747-009-0138-0.
- Salim, A.A., (2023) Employee retention in light of green human resources practice (GHRM) through the intervening role of work engagement. *Annals of Contemporary Development in HR*, vol. 2(4). <https://acdmhr.theiaer.org/archive/v2/v2n4/p2.html>.
- Shah, S.Q.A. Lai, F.W. Shad, M.K. Konečná, Z. Goni, F.A. Chofreh, A.G.&Klemeš, J.J. (2021) The Inclusion of Intellectual Capital into the Green Board Committee to Enhance Firm Performance. *Sustainability*, 131, 10849. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910849>.
- Singh K. and Misra M. (2021) Linking corporate social responsibility (CSR) and organizational performance: The moderating effect of corporate reputation. *Eur. Res. Manag. Bus. Econ.*vol.27, 100-139.
- Singh, D., A literature review on employee retention with focus on recent trends. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, Vol. 6 (1):425-431.
- Singh, D., A literature review on employee retention with focus on recent trends. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, 6 (1):425-431.
- Smith, A., &Toffel, M. W. (2021). Small and medium-sized enterprises and environmental stewardship. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 46, 205-232.
- Sueyoshi T, Goto M, Wang D. (2017) Malmquist index measurement for sustainability enhancement in Chinese municipalities and providence. *Energy Econ.* vol.67: 71-554.
- Syed Quaid, A. S., Fong-Woon L, Muhammad, K. S., Zdeňka, K., Feybi, A. G., Abdoulmohammad, G. C and Jiří. J. K. (2021).
- Ullah, M.M. (2017). Integrating Environmental Sustainability into Human Resources Management: A Comprehensive Review on Green Human Resources Management (Green HRM) Practices. *Economics and Management*.
- UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme). (2022). Environmental stewardship. Retrieved from <https://www.unep.org/explore-topics/sustainable-development-goals/why-it-matters/environmental-stewardship>

Original Article

- Uyar, A.; Kilic, M.; Koseoglu, M.A.; Kuzey, C.; Karaman, A.S. (2020) The link among board characteristics, corporate social responsibility performance, and financial performance: Evidence from the hospitality and tourism industry. *Tour. Manag. Perspect.* Vol.35, 100714.
- Wang, L. Ur Rehman, A., Xu, Z. Amjad, F., Ur Rehman, S. (2023) Green Corporate Governance, green finance, and sustainable performance nexus in Chinese SMES: A mediation moderation model. *Sustainability*, 15-09914.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su15139914>
- Weian Li, Jian Xu and Minna Z (2018) Green Governance: New Perspective from Open Innovation *Sustainability*10, 3845; doi:10.3390/su10113845 www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability
- Welchman, R. (2012). "Environmental stewardship." In M. L. V. Martens & M. North (Eds.), *encyclopedia of environmental management*. doi:10.4135/9781412993993.n125.
- Westman L. Luederitz C. Kundurpi A. Mercado A.J. Weber O. Burch S.L. (2019) Conceptualizing businesses as social actors: A framework for understanding sustainability actions in small-and medium-sized enterprises. *Bus. Strategy Environ.*28, 388–402.
- Wijesiri, N.R.A.S.S., Paranagama G.S., Sirirwardhana M.M.A.S., Thilakarathna, R.S. & Weerathna D.L.N.C. (2018). The impact of HR Practices on Employee Retention, a Case of BPO Sector. *Sri Lanka International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 9(1)
- Wu, L., Wang, L., Philipsen, N.J and Fang X (2023) The impact of eco-innovation on environmental performance in different regional settings: new evidence from Chinese cities: *Journal of environment, Development and Sustainability*. On-line journal. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-027-04280-z>.
- Wu, Y. Hu, K and Zhang, J (2021) Environmental stewardship and SMEs: A review and research agenda. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 318, 128611.
- Xu S and Zhu H (2022) Does green governance efficiency and green finance policies matters in sustainable environment: Implication for public health. *Frontiers Public Health* 10:349-861.
- Yousuf, S., & Siddiqui, D. A. (2019) Factors Influencing Employee Retention: A Karachi Based Comparative Study on IT and Banking Industry. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 9, (1): 42-62.
- Zahoor, M., & Ijaz, M (2015). Impact of human resource management practices on employee retention in Telecom Sector of Pakistan. *Journal of resource development and management*, vol.8:1-9. <https://www.iiste.org/journal/index.php/JRDM/25981/26337>.

Original Article

Zeidan, S. &Itani, N. (2020) Cultivating employee engagement in organizations: Development of a conceptual framework. *Central European Management Journal*, 28 (1):99-118.

Zhu Q. Zou F. and Zhang P. (2019) The role of innovation for performance improvement through corporate social responsibility practices among small and medium-sized suppliers in China. *Corporate, Social, Responsible & Environmental Management*. 26, 341–350.

Zubair, S., & Khan, M.A. (2018). Green human resources management: A review and framework for future research. *International Journal of business and Management*, vol. 13(7): 1-12.<https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v13n7p1>.

APPENDIX

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Green Human Resource Management Practices and Employee Retention in Plastic Firms in Anambra State

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Likert Scale Option					Total
		SA	A	D	SD	UND	
1.	Green Human Resources Management (GHRM) practice is a series of practices, processes and policies that encourage the sustainable behavior of an employee through training and development which results to profit and yields for the venture.						
2.	It is environmentally friendly strategies that enhance environmental sustainability and retention of employees						
3.	GHRM practice by organizations reduce turnover rate of employees and stop them from leaving the organization.						
4.	GHRM practices aimed at fostering employee commitment to an organization.						
5.	It has helpful in boost my firm’s image, encourage self-confidence among workers, increase productivity, reduce costs, minimize waste, and save time.						
	Total						

Note: (SA = Strongly agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree; SD = Strongly disagree and UND = Undecided).

Original Article

Environmental Stewardship and Eco-innovation in Plastic Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Likert Scale Option					Total
		SA	A	D	SD	UN D	
1.	Environmental stewardship entails taking action to accommodate and balance the requirements of various groups, while also ensuring the consistent conservation and responsible use of natural resources.						
2.	It is a blend of approaches, activities, behaviors, and technologies utilized to safeguard, restore, or sustainably utilize the environment as a means to enhance business processes and achieve innovative advantages.						
3.	It is implemented through adopting eco-friendly technologies that reduces waste generation, and implementing sustainable supply chain practices.						
4.	It is expected to represents a collective responsibility toward the environment, reflected in an organization's policies, procedures, and actions regarding relationships with employees and customers.						
5.	It provides value to customers and businesses, while also significantly reducing environmental impacts.						
	Total						

Note: (SA = Strongly agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree; SD = Strongly disagree and UND = Undecided).

Original Article

Dependent Variable: Sustainability of Firms in the SMEs Sector

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Likert Scale Options				Total	
		VGE	GE	ME	LE	VL E	
1.	To what extent do you agree that green HRM practices can lead to employee retention in Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State?						
2.	To what extent do you agree that environmental stewardship can lead to Eco-innovation in Plastic Manufacturing firms in Anambra State?						
	Total						

Note: (VGE = Very great extent; GE = Great extent; ME = Moderate extent; LE = Little extent and VLE = Very little extent).